
Implementing Recommendations at the Faculty of Education, University of Benghazi (UoB): Action Research Methods to Enhance the Desired Reform Strategy

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Abstract

This associated research aims to obtain a greater understanding and awareness of the findings and recommendations resulting from the previously published field research paper entitled "Repercussions of the Continuous Instability for the Quality of Education in the State of Libya: An Investigational Study within the Faculty of Education, University of Benghazi (UoB)" by Elabbar (2022), which broadly found profound impacts of the ongoing instability on the quality of the education process and knowledge management among students, teaching assistants (TAs), lecturers, and administrators at the Faculty of Education, UoB. The study exposed a "real educational deficiency in the temporal pool and the knowledge shares acquired by and granted to secondary education students in Benghazi who entered the Faculty of Education in recent years compared to what they

should be" (Elabbar, 2022, pp. 4–5). As it went through various other findings, such as a lack of learning facilities, almost no professional development programs, and negative repercussions resulting from the faculty's transition from the annual system to the semester system "under force majeure conditions that the city of Benghazi passed through from 2014 to 2017" (Elabbar, 2022, p. 5), no bridge between the school system and the university system was found that could have enabled both systems to work together to overcome the problems of poor quality of education in the entire state of Libya, not just the university of Benghazi. Inaction by ministry policymakers and directors may result in the rapid collapse of the education system if the existing complications are not addressed. Thus, this action research aims to implement and reevaluate several of the proposed suggestions within the Faculty of Education, UoB, in general,

and the English Department, UoB, in particular. This will support the role of the Faculty of Education in advocating the desired gradual reform strategy for the entire education system in Libya by encouraging the transition from theory to practice. In addition, this research collects and analyzes action data using four methodological mechanisms. The first mechanism works with preservice teachers who are gaining teaching experience in five primary and secondary schools in Benghazi. The second mechanism works with seven higher education coordinators, including the researcher, who are currently working on launching MA (Master of Arts) and M Sc (Master of Sciences) programs at the Faculty of Education. The third mechanism works with six T.A.s in the English Department who are involved in a bridge program for first-semester students. The fourth mechanism works with an existing interactive idea developed by one of the English Department educators, Mrs. Jwaili, who has adopted a new method of presenting EFL (English as a Foreign Language) teaching and learning to preservice teachers. The study produced several recommendations to be incorporated into the projected gradual reform plan formulated by Elabbar (2017). It sustained until it reached its innovative form in 2022, entitled "Reforming the Libyan Education System: Seven Articulated Years Via a Strategic Planning Pyramid." Additionally, this study suggests adopting action research

as a model of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and employing corrective procedures to compensate for identified weaknesses within the Faculty of Education and among all its members.

Keywords: Transforming suggestions into practice, four methodological mechanisms, four action research processes as CPD processes, an innovative, resilient policy for the entire projected education reform plan, the whole education system could collapse if immediate action is not taken.

A. Research Questions, Focal Points, and Goals

As stated previously, this study aims to assess the severity of the identified problems and the viability of some of the solutions proposed in the previous research paper. The following research questions reflect the necessity of this study:

- 1) Can we gradually introduce professional development and reform ideas into the context of

education in Libya, which faces enormous challenges?

- 2) How applicable are the recommendations suggested by previous research, and are there any additional unforeseen obstacles?

The objectives of this study are the following:

- 1) To practically evaluate the proposed suggestions at the same research ground (the Faculty of Education) to gain a deeper understanding and determine whether the theory can be translated into practice.
- 2) To establish action research as a model of Continuous Professional Development (CPD) within the Faculty of Education.
- 3) To comprehensively understand how to reform complex education and management systems, such as the Libyan education system.
- 4) To incorporate additional ideas and dynamic strategies regarding the role of the Faculty of Education into the required process for reforming the entire education system in Libya;
- 5) To encourage more researchers, educators, teaching assistants (TAs), and master's and doctoral students to debate and expand their interest in employing transformative professional development strategies.

B. Combined Literature in Brief

Due to the pragmatic nature of this field research in terms of its goals, focal points, and four methodological mechanisms, each of these mechanisms underwent action research steps as a model of CPD. As a result, this part will theoretically and briefly illustrate Libya's educational status and the developed qualitative tools utilized within the study framework.

1. Libyan Educational Status

Their research indicated that (1) the Libyan curricula need to be aligned with a well-executed educational strategy and (2) a significant portion of the Libyan curricula are imported from Singaporean curricula (demonstrating a different culture and style of teaching and learning). Malabar (2019) explained that the effects of government bureaucracy, culture, and social interference on education organizations and administration are deeply rooted.

Moreover, Elabbar (2022) found that "after the declaration of the Government of National Unity (GNU; March 2021), nothing has changed except a reorganization splitting the Ministry of Education into three separate ministries (Ministry of Education, Ministry of Higher Education, and Ministry of Vocational Education)." This was created for political purposes and did nothing to resolve the profoundly rooted challenges.

2. Qualitative Research, Tools, and Analysis

Wolff (2021) showed that qualitative

approaches are typically more adaptable, allowing for greater spontaneity and “adaptation of the interaction between the researcher and the study participant, as qualitative methods ask typically ‘open-ended’ questions that are not necessarily worded in the same way with each participant. With open-ended questions, participants are free to respond in their own words, and these responses tend to be more complex than simply ‘yes’ or ‘no.’ Also, Qualitative data analysis tools can help you categorize, process, and examine data for actionable insights.” Flick (2002) stated that qualitative research is more helpful in exploring “why” than “how many” (p. 4). Davis (1995) explained that qualitative research is interpretive and not predetermined (p. 429). Pope and Mays (1995) defined qualitative research as the development of concepts that enable us to recognize “social phenomena in natural rather than experimental settings, giving due emphasis to the meanings, experiences, and views of the participants” (pp. 44–45). Nigatu (2009) demonstrated that qualitative data analysis is the range of processes and procedures by which we move from gathered qualitative data to an explanation, sense, or interpretation of the situations we are examining (p. 22). Qualitative data analysis aims to explore the semantic and symbolic content of the qualitative data, typically based on an interpretive philosophy.

2. Action Research Tactics

Mills (2007) defines “action research” as “any systematic inquiry made by

teachers, researchers, principals, education counselors, or other stakeholders in the teaching/learning environment to gather information about how their schools operate, how they teach, and how well their students learn” (p.32). Frost et al. (2003) explained that “action research is a process of systematic reflection, inquiry and action carried out by individuals about their professional practice” (p.25).

Guskey (2000) stated, “The idea of action research is that educational problems and issues are best identified and investigated where the action is: at the classroom and school level.

Clare et al. (2000) claimed that the action research approach could improve teachers’ knowledge in several ways:

- They develop close relationships with their students, interact with them, observe them, and gather data.

Brien (1998) showed that “action research is known by many other names, including ‘participatory research,’ ‘collaborative inquiry,’ ‘emancipator research,’ ‘action research learning,’ and ‘contextual action research.’” He has defined action research as “learning by doing,” in which a group of teachers identify a problem, take action to solve it, evaluate the success of their efforts, and, if they are not satisfied, try again (pp.3–5). According to Boreham (2004), the research process is a developmental process that includes identifying a problematic issue, imagining a possible solution, testing it, evaluating it, and

changing practice in light of the evaluation (p.55).

C. Methodological Tactics: Action Procedures and Functional Mechanisms

As stated previously, the purpose of this study is to implement several significant recommendations from a previous study and to collect additional information regarding the status of the once-recommended seven-year reform of the entire Libyan education system (proposed and published by Elabbar in September 2022). As a result, this study employs four methodological mechanisms to utilize

Figure 1

Implementation of Action Research as a Model of CPD

1. Data Collection Mechanisms

1.1. The First Data Collection Mechanism: Field Training Program

In this data collection mechanism, the researcher worked with fourteen (14) preservice EFL (English as a Foreign Language) teachers who are gaining teaching experience (*practicum*) at five primary and secondary schools in the city of Benghazi, as these three months of

action research steps as a model of CPD. It developed qualitative data collection procedures and mechanisms as collection tools designed to interact directly with the targeted educational environment and personnel. These combined phases will be produced by four action research measures (the only model of CPD) and four functional mechanisms intended to facilitate the researcher's interaction with challenges, the existing culture, beliefs, and even anticipated difficulties and results. Figure 1 shows the implementation of action research as a model of CPD.

(*Separate & Continued*) fieldwork are a prerequisite for graduation from the Faculty of Education. The researcher was already part of the department's practicum program. The preservice teachers' were trained to employ the following:

- A. Classroom evaluation based on the primary research objectives added to the faculty's official field study evaluation and reflection forms.
- B. Generate in-class managed research (their teaching opportunity) using innovatively designed lesson plans, teaching aids, and controlled interactive education approaches to serve the research purposes. All productions are described in a reflection form prepared by the researcher.
- C. Researcher's interviews and focus groups with schoolteachers, social workers, school administrators, inspectors, and the faculty's field study directors and supervisors of the 14 preservice teachers before and after the practicum.

1.2. The Second Data Collection Mechanism: Investigating the Utilized Bridge Program

In this mechanism, the researcher worked with seven (7) T.A.s and three (3) of their supervisors in the English Department of the Faculty of Education at UoB. This program was established in the department in 2020 for first-and second-semester students to promote core subjects and provide newcomers with an intensive education to compensate for the knowledge they lost during the country's years of instability. In addition, the department aimed to involve its T.A.s in implementing interactive and practice-

based education. Thus, T.A.s and their supervisors were discussed, evaluated, and interviewed. They were also invited to participate in a focus group, perform document analysis of the added materials, and revise the printed department bridge program strategy. (Before conducting this field research, the researcher was a department staff member who suggested and oversaw this program and the additional materials.)

1.3. The Third Data Collection Mechanism: A Newly Launched Master of Arts and Master of Sciences Program

In this data collection mechanism, the researcher worked with eight (8) higher education coordinators (including the researcher as coordinator of higher education studies representing the English Department). Before the official launch of the new M.A. program at the Faculty of Education (in September 2023, as planned), all coordinators and the head of the higher education office are currently (2022) working on the final details. The researcher conducted an intensive document analysis of the entire program's regulations, VMAs, and how they were created. The researcher then conducted numerous interviews and focus groups with department coordinators, administrators, and master's candidates, in addition to personal participation in all phases of program development. In addition to the research's primary objectives, this data collection instrument

aimed to obtain in-depth information about the value of offering higher education studies in the Faculty of Education and its relationship with labor market demand.

1.4. The Fourth Data Collection Mechanism: Investigating Jwaili's Modern Strategy

The fourth data collection mechanism utilized an existing interactive idea developed by one of the influential English Department educators, Mrs. Aisha Jwaili, who innovated new approach to presenting teaching and learning English among first-and second-semester students at the Faculty of Education entitled "Incentive Course." She intended to "up level" her students' presentation, speaking, and fluency skills by adopting several creative ideas and inviting native English guest teachers to teach and profoundly interact with her students under her leadership. She

intended to change the existing faculty's dissatisfied attitude toward education.

In addition, with only moral support from the department, she managed to compensate for the current lack of teaching aids and learning facilitation by implementing incentive learning in terms of presented subjects (motivating topics), coaching methods, unique classroom management, and self-brought teaching aids. The researcher utilized four data collection tools to obtain additional ideas and feedback regarding Jwaili's incentive strategy and related VMAs. These tools were interdependent: focus groups, unstructured interviews, student feedback sheets, and group discussions.

D. Data Analysis

The data analysis processes were categorized based on the four mechanisms of data collection methodologies and their connected tools. As the enormous amount of collected data underwent two main analytical phases (induction and elicitation) before selecting valuable data to be examined and then summarized, it was necessary to investigate and then summarize only the most pertinent information. Table 1 shows a summary of the classification of each mechanism and its associated tools.

Table 1

Data Analysis Classifications and Methods

<i>Data Analysis Classifications and Methods</i>			
<i>First Mechanism</i>	<i>Second Mechanism</i>	<i>Third Mechanism</i>	<i>Fourth Mechanism</i>

<p>1) <i>MG analysis of the collected 101 evaluation sheets from fourteen (14) preservice teachers and the researcher.</i></p> <p>2) <i>I am analyzing sixty-six (66) designed reflection sheets and designed lessons obtained from in-classroom teaching.</i></p> <p>3) <i>Interviews and focus groups: scripting and analysis. The researcher conducted over nineteen (19) unstructured interviews and administered eleven (11) focus groups with teachers, administrators, inspectors, preservice teachers, graduates, social workers, and parents.</i></p> <p>4) <i>This mechanism produced seven (7) clear</i></p>	<p>1) <i>Document analysis of the department's planned core materials, printed bridge program strategy, and teacher feedback notes. Discourse analysis of the developed materials performed by the researcher based on these research goals.</i></p> <p>2) <i>The scripting and analysis of the determined interviews focus groups, teaching assistants, and their supervisors 'reflections.</i></p> <p>3) <i>This mechanism produced six (6) clear and essential findings.</i></p>	<p>1) <i>In-depth analysis of the M.A. and M Sc documents and regulations.</i></p> <p>2) <i>Scripting and analyzing the established interviews and focus groups with the departments' coordinators, administrators, and candidates.</i></p> <p>3) <i>This mechanism produced six (6) clear and essential findings.</i></p>	<p>2) <i>Content analysis of the collected data from the Incentive Course established by Aisha Jwaili, including discourse analysis of the provided materials .</i></p> <p>3) <i>Scripting interviews and focus groups based on research may be the focal point.</i></p> <p>4) <i>They are classifying program evaluation sheets, guest speakers, and student reflections.</i></p>
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<i>findings.</i>			5) This mechanism produced four (4) clear and essential findings.
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E. Findings

The results of this study were attained through the application of four methodological mechanisms and their corresponding qualitative data collection tools. The researcher has uncovered in greater depth the findings of his previous field research at the Faculty of Education, UoB ,entitled“ *Repercussions of the Continuous Instability for the Quality of Education in the State of Libya: An Investigational Study within the Faculty of Education, University of Benghazi.*”These pervasive, continuous challenges have had a significant impact on and continue to substantially affect the entire educational process at the University of Benghazi, specifically the Faculty of Education. These thoroughly documented challenges can be summed up as follows:

1) A lack of teaching facilities, aids, updated libraries, internet access, and a sense of community on campus, as well as the cultural effects of education, have frustrated the majority of students, who come to campus only to pass exams and obtain a certificate rather than to acquire knowledge.

- 2) Bureaucratic administration from the ministry, university, and faculty in terms of education regulations had a considerable effect that nearly paralyzed most desires for change or even suggesting reform proposals into practice, as all public universities in Libya continue to follow centralized regulations that have not been improved or further developed since their first establishment in 2001.
- 3) Due to ongoing political upheavals and an outdated administration philosophy, most education authorities today do not care as much as they should about the substandard quality of education. They only administer the beginning and end of the study, and almost none of the stated quality and assurance instructions are followed precisely. Even when some of the instructions are implemented, it is evident that schools and universities need help to comply with them.
- 4) There is no offered professional development or managed training for professors, T.A.s, and new educators. Some of them have lost their scholarship opportunities due to the

current instability in the country. As a result, most of them (particularly T.A.s) only come to the faculty if they are called for administrative work or optional initiatives.

- 5) New-generation educators and employees have a strong desire for change. Many students are willing to accept gradual reform if the authorities facilitate it, but they still need to do so.

1. First Mechanism: Fundamental Findings

- 1) Tiny shared strategies or coordination exist between the school system and the university system, preventing the formation of an interactive plan from supporting education input, output, or reform activities. In addition, there is a significant lack of adequate teaching aids and learning facilities within schools and even at the Faculty of Education. This has resulted in an apparent deficiency and a low standard of education. In addition to the absence of constant academic reports and almost no professional development workshops for schoolteachers, social workers, and even inspectors to discuss academic challenges, this led to ineffective individual work.
- 2) Most school and university administrations are focused only on the beginning and end of the study and completing the curriculum, with no practical focus on the quality of education except for individual initiatives that have been proven

effective. In addition, the study found that several students and schoolteachers are profoundly affected by state instability in terms of professional development (for teachers) and the unproductive roles of parents and social workers; these factors led to an evident loss of motivation and the capacity to advance in several cases at the studied schools.

- 3) Numerous English language teachers, who needed more professional qualifications to teach, taught English in Arabic and focused solely on homework and memorization.
- 4) There is no organized policy of school administration (leadership), except for the start and end of the study and the content focus, as both preservice teachers and the researcher found different impacts among evaluated schools, indicating that the schools are personally administered. In other words, schools are administered by the administration culture in Libya, and there is almost no policy or specific educational goals besides passing exams and completing “ministry-provided unrelated course books,” as stated by numerous teachers and inspectors.
- 5) Except when being evaluated by inspectors, most EFL teachers we have encountered do not use lesson plans, interactive learning, or teaching aids in their lessons. Some of them provided justifications such as “lack of facilities,” “a large number of

students,” “students’ learning styles,” and “heads of schools’ instructions to keep class as quiet as possible and focus on finishing the units on time.”

- 6) EFL preservice teachers at the Faculty of Education initially found it challenging to present the improved lesson plan and implement the planned (by the researcher) communicative education within the targeted schools. Some were dissatisfied with the “school environment,” “students’ learning styles,” “and the way education is structured. For example, one of the T.A.s said, “Some teachers tried to hide their weaknesses and continued to focus on particular students during my attendance; then, the students told me that their teacher changed her behavior solely because I was present.” However, after a few weeks, four of the preservice teachers observed “slightly positive” responses from the students, mainly when they offered (self-brought) aids and treated the students differently than they had in the past.
- 7) Through all the collected documents, interviews, and focus groups, it is evident that neither the university nor the schools have an education policy and that teachers and students are dissatisfied with the current state of education and would like to see restructuring plans and professional ideas implemented to reform the entire Libyan education system.

2. Second Mechanism: Fundamental Findings

- 1) Again, it is demonstrated that there is no bridge between the school and university systems. This bridge would have allowed both systems to work together to address the poor quality of education in Libya in general and in Benghazi in particular. Possibly only the English Department at the Faculty of Education has previously adopted (on department members’ initiative) a development plan focusing on supporting “newcomers with core materials of intensive teach,” connecting interested T.A.s to participate in after-class education and reevaluating the entire course syllabus. The concept of the bridge program has demonstrated its effectiveness as a type of reform, but it still faces several organizational obstacles.
- 2) As stated by one of the program directors, this research instrument revealed that the cognitive abilities of most newly admitted students to the Faculty of Education are comparable to those of eighth-grade students, with a few exceptions. However, when they participated in the department’s self-initiative bridge program, which aimed to support the core subjects and methods of teaching fundamental issues by adopting interactive lectures and monitoring their implementation, their performance quickly improved

- compared to students who did not participate in such a program.
- 3) Unfortunately, it was discovered that the English Department's bridge program did not receive explicit support from the faculty or even from other departments, as some "think that this program is a waste of students' time." One faculty member stated, "Weak students should take on their responsibilities, not those of their departments." In addition, the department faces issues such as a complete lack of facilities, teaching aids, and classrooms.
 - 4) Most participants (the newcomer students) in the program are influenced by their learning culture because, after realizing that this program is a departmental initiative, they ignored attendance until the department implemented attendance grades. Moreover, as a result of the instability of the scholarship program, some T.A.s has expressed their reluctance to continue participating in this program because they have "lost a lot of time waiting for a scholarship or completing their masters in the faculty." These issues have influenced the motivation of the remaining teachers in the department to continue the bridge program.
 - 5) The feedback sheets indicated that the goal of the proposed bridge program was highly valued, and it would be even more valuable if the ministry or university supported it. Still, they have never done so as of yet.
 - 6) Students who participated in the challenged bridge program are now familiar with the determined level and have transitioned smoothly to the subsequent semesters compared to students who did not participate. However, the entire department still faces significant obstacles, such as a lack of materials, aids, and bureaucratic management (top-down), which impede any efforts or initiatives toward development or change.

3. Third Mechanism: Fundamental Findings

- 1) There are no facilities, no internet, and even a shortage of qualified teachers (specializing in education) in some departments, causing some departments' faculty to seriously consider delaying their planned start date.
- 2) The postgraduate office faces significant bureaucratic challenges in terms of administration and the proficiencies of some department coordinators. As some of them are influenced by the Libyan education culture (only content focus), this issue has significantly impacted the entire program's future before it has even begun.
- 3) Due to the circumstances that the Libyan state has endured and continues to endure, the majority of scholarship (studying abroad) decrees related to the faculty have been postponed, resulting in overcrowding

in the departments and the inability of the majority of faculty members to organize educational work that helps them expand their research and academic perspectives within the country. As a result of a lack of assigned tasks, a number of them reached a level of near-reluctance to attend their departments.

- 4) Some of the English Department T.A.s took their postgraduate courses at the Faculty of Languages, which differed from the methods suggested by the Faculty of Education; as a result, they could not support the Faculty of Education's goals due to their bureaucratic roles.
- 5) Almost no practical or technical mechanism contributes to defining a general strategy for postgraduate studies from which a vision, mission, and long-term foundational and progress goals emerge, which produce plans and programs that address the needs of the future labor market and pave the way for the adoption of educational topics and methods. The researcher discovered that the postgraduate program only meets the quality and assurance standards used by all public universities without a clear focus on the challenges faced by the labor market.
- 6) Even with these obstacles (lack of facilities, lack of supervisors, and even the state's uncertain political future), many T.A.s are prepared (they have no other choice) to begin

the M.A. program. In addition, some highly qualified staff members are working hard to make all active ideas for the postgraduate program as helpful as possible. They have developed some administration roles to be more adaptable and dynamic.

4. Fourth Mechanism: Fundamental Findings

- 1) The Incentive Course, designed by Aisha Jwaili, a member of the department's staff, elicited positive feedback from students and guest speakers, as she incorporated new information on broader topics not previously covered in their curricula. However, she faced no assistance from the faculty administration and received only moral support from the department.
- 2) The researcher found that the participant's feedback on the implemented teaching methods and the atmosphere was encouraging, and they wanted to see similar activities in their other classes.
- 3) The materials were intended to enhance the student's knowledge and proficiency in speech and working in an interactive setting.
- 4) Due to bureaucratic difficulties and a lack of teaching facilities, the program might be discontinued.

F. Conclusion and Suggestions

As stated previously, the purpose of this study is to reexamine, implement, and evaluate several of the proposed suggestions within the Faculty of

Education, UoB, in general, and the English Department, UoB, in particular. This is also intended to support the role of the Faculty of Education in promoting the desired gradual reform strategy for the entire education system in Libya. If the study were used and supported by the ministry as an essential part of the reform, it would have many positive effects, as it demonstrated strong need to reform the entire education system in Libya in all aspects. In addition, it reactivates the seven-year plan for gradual reform proposed by Elabbar (2022). In other words, this critical situation necessitates a fundamental rethink by all members of the Libyan education system in an "unusual" manner that begins with scientific process steps. First, it is essential to establish the foundations and principles of comprehensive educational reform for the entire education system while simultaneously promoting greater awareness of the significance of professional development among educators, administrators, and policymakers. Second, the improvement of educational content is crucial, and the Ministry of Education must work diligently to develop all necessary roles and emphasize the significance of education faculties and CPD. Third, the Faculty of Education must adopt general policies and a curriculum that enhance the goals of increasing the productivity of faculty members, TAs, decisions, and study plans simultaneously. Fourth, it is essential to implement monitoring and

follow-up mechanisms and to evaluate the performance and quality of education at all levels. Finally, it is crucial to note that the entire Libyan education system is on the verge of collapse unless the government takes immediate reform measures.

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